

True Love Needs No Potion

Setting: The play is set in a time after 'The Midsummer Night's Dream' where the characters have left their children in the care of a nanny who is later revealed to be Puck, the fairy.

Scene 1

[Children playing with each other, some are sharing a skip rope, few are running here and there, making a lot of noise, a few in the back can play some hand clapping game while reciting the corresponding rhyme.]

[A lady walks from the right. Looks at the children and takes the centre stage as she says the following lines.]

Nanny: Alright alright gather around now, its story time.....

[The children¹ stand on either side of the nanny]

Child 1: Ayyyyy!It's story time.

Child 2: Nanny, always tell us good stories.

Child 3: I dont wanna listen to fairy tales.

Child 2: I dont wanna listen to fairy tales.

Child 1: Yes, I don't wanna listen to fairy tales.

Nanny: Ok, what do you want to listen to today?

Child 1: Hmmm... I want to listen to a monster story (*roars*)

Child 2: Oh no! I'm scared of monsters.

Child 3: I want to listen to a love story.

Nanny: Oh! I have a great love story for you. (*moves dramatically to the center of the stage.*)

It was a dark and gloomy night. The moon shone upon the dark trees in the forest. From a distance a small light entered the weary love birds in search of shelter and love...

¹ The script only has the dialogues of three children, but there can be more children involved as well.

[The children on the stage and the nanny exit the stage through the right.]

[Lysander and Hermia enter in a hurry at the sound of the wind on the upper stage from the left and move to the center of the stage.]

[Lysander and Hermia panting]

Lysander: My love, I have good and bad news for you. Which one would you like to hear first?

Hermia: *(panting, irritated)* What is it ?

Lysander: Good or Bad, my dear ?

Hermia: Good one, of course. *(still panting)*

Lysander: Ah! We are now far away from Athena, so far that your father won't find us. *(beaming with pride)*

Hermia: And the bad one?

Lysander: Oh !*(panicking)* I am afraid we are too far away that we are lost.

[Hermia sitting down, worried]

Lysander: It's too dark my dear. I think we must sleep now.

[He walks closer to Hermia, and sits down closer to her with love in his eyes, Hermia shyness away from Lysander, but does not move away from him, but turns her head away from him coyly.]

Hermia: My love, I would love to fall asleep in your arms. But for my sake please sleep a little farther away from me.*(coy)*

Lysander *(defeated):* Anything for you, my lady.

[He walks down the stage and stops in the right side of the lower stage and sleeps on there facing Hermia]

Hermia: Goodnight, sweetheart.

Lysander: Goodnight, my darling.

[Both sleep facing each other]

Scene 2

[From the left of the lower stage, Demetrius enters the stage, in a hurry to find Lysander and Hermia. He stops in the centre of the stage. Helena runs behind Demetrius and stops behind him, pleading]²

Helena: Stop, Demetrius ! Stop even if only you had to kill me for it.

[Helena holds Demetrius's leg and pleads]

Demetrius : I'm telling you to get out of here. I don't love you. *[Not facing Helena]*

Lysander (sleep talking): Hermia, Hermia, my love, you shine like the stars in the sky.

[Demetrius in rage shouts and tries to move towards the sound]

Helena (pleads): No Demetrius , please don't go. I will be alone in the dark.

Demetrius: I don't care

[He kicks Helena, and exits the stage. While Helena whimpers and slowly picks herself up and pursues Demetrius]

² In the spirit of using the entire stage one can even make these characters enter from among the audience, to add more magic and suspense to the play.

Scene 3

[On the balcony opposite to the stage, or on the upper stage]³

[Oberon and Puck busy talking on the other side; Titania walks in and clears her throat to grab their attention]

Oberon *(turning surprised)*: How not nice to see you? *(sarcastically)*

Titania : Oh! I see you are jealous , that I swore not to sleep with you. Or talk to you and I kept my word. *(boastful)*

Oberon: Or are you jealous that I came all the way from Fairyland to celebrate the wedding of my so-called- warrior-lover Hippolyta?

Titania: You will never get the young child *(irritated)*, he is my worshipper's child. And I will not give him up, for your petty tricks. *(storms off)*

[Oberon hits the railing in anguish]

[Titania slowly walks toward the stage and sits by one of the entrances]

[Puck stands behind Oberon all this while and supports his decisions with facial expressions and actions to add more humor to the plot]

³ If the performance stage does not have a balcony or a similar stage opposite to the stage where the play has been performed. Then the upper stage where Hermia is sleeping can be used. If the upper stage does not have adequate space. Hermia can be removed from the stage while she sleeps by the stage crew and replaced during scene 6.

Scene 4

[Puck looks anxiously at his master and awaits for his command]

Puck: Master, What do we do now ?

Oberon (*pauses*): Remember the flower we talked about one day, that flower the ladies call the love-in-idleness?

Puck: The flower on which poor cupid's arrow fell and it turned from being white to purple?

[In the lower stage, Demetrius runs into the stage shouting]

Demetrius : Hermia, Hermia where are you? (*Rage*)

[On the upper stage]

Oberon: Yes, It's said that if its juice was applied on the eyes of someone. They will fall in love with the next creature they see. (*Oberon and Puck laugh*)

[In the lower stage, Hermia runs after Demetrius]

Helena: Demetrius, Demetrius stop going after them please. (*still pleading*)

[On the upper stage]

Puck: Wait, you want me to get it ?

[In the lower stage]

Demetrius: Stop it women, why on earth will you follow me when I don't want you?

[On the upper stage]

Oberon: I suppose it can be useful for some.

[Turning to face the couple standing down, while Puck exits. Demetrius and Helena are in the lower stage in the centre.]⁴

⁴ The dialogue delivery in this scene must be quick, to add a slight humor to the play. To ensure this quick dialogue delivery happens, make sure that the actors get the cue of their line from the last word of the previous line.

Scene 5

[In continuation of the previous scene, in the lower stage]

Helena: It's because *(pause)* I love you.

Demetrius: Well, I didn't love you at all.

Helena *(moving closer)(anger):* Demetrius... Look into my eyes and say that you never felt loved, when you were there with me.

Demetrius *(looking at Helena) (pause) :* I didn't love you at all.

[Helena collapses on the floor and starts to cry and sleeps, while Demetrius takes few steps away]

[From the upper stage]

Oberon: Don't worry my child, before he leaves the forest you'll change places. You'll be the one running away and he'll be in love with you.

[And casts a spell⁵ to make Demetrius sleep, Demetrius sleeps a few steps away from Lysander in the lower stage.]

[From the lower stage]

Puck: Master, Master *(screaming)*

[From the upper stage]

Oberon: Quite you fool *(irritated)*

[From the lower stage]

Puck: I got the flower *[Shows the flower with both his hands to Oberon]*

[From the upper stage]

Oberon: Now I will apply its juice on Titania's eyes and you go and apply it on the eyes of the Athenian man and meet me by dawn .

[Both exit]

⁵ To add to the magic of the play, while Oberon casts a spell, he can sprinkle glitter instead of making hand gestures.

Scene 6⁶

[Puck walks among the audience and asks a few in the audience to apply the Potion. It sometimes assesses the audience to find the Athenian man. Oberon on the other hand apprehends Puck and hides on the left side of the upper stage.]

[Titania and her fellow fairies enter the stage from the left side of the upper stage and they sleep on the left side of the upper stage while holding the child closer to her. The other fairies are around her in a semi circle admiring their Queen sleep]

[Oberon casts a spell that makes the fairies to sleep, and he accompanied by Puck removes the child and gestures Puck to apply the potion, but Puck's antics make him grab the potion and apply it himself]

[Meanwhile Bottom, the carpenter and his friends enter the left side of the lower stage. Bottom takes the lead, meanwhile the other carpenters sit down on the lower left side of the stage with their back facing the audience. As he is talking, the ones accompanying Bottom fall asleep as they are listening to his speech.]

Bottom : We are putting up a play for our beloved king and queen on their wedding day. It must be grand , fantastic and the king and queen must reward us for the performance. I know we don't have enough time. But we when .. we LL GATHER TOGETHER AND WORK. We can finish it in no time. I have a couple of sample scripts here would you like to.....

[Oberon sends Puck down stairs to apply the potion on to the Athenian man. Puck after landing down stairs to the lower stage on the right is confused as to whom he must apply the potion.]

⁶ The following might be confusing to read but it is easier to remember, if one can understand that whatever happens with Puck, Oberon and Titania are on the upper stage and the lower stage is entirely for Bot and his crew. Bot's speech is the background score of this scene as there are no dialogues for Oberon and Puck here.

It will be advisable to the director to ask the audience to fall asleep however they like while Bot is performing his inspiring speech, in this way, your audience also feels a part of the play.

[Bottom realises that the entire audience has slept throughout his speech and is angry]

Bottom: YOU GUYS ARE SLEEPING. OH MY GOD!!! GUYS WE HAVE COME ALL THE WAY OUT OF ATHENA TO SLEEP. I UNDERSTAND YOU GUYS ARE TIRED. BUT READ THE SCRIPTS . UNTIL I GET BACK.

[Bottom exits left of the lower stage]

[As he is screaming Puck applies the potion on Lysander's eyes and runs away]

[Helena wakes up in the commotion and starts to cry]

Helena: Demetrius , Demetrius.....

[Lysander wakes up, rubs his eyes and look at Helena]

Lysander : Oh my God! Helena I never knew you looked so beautiful. I wish I carried a sword , so I could murder him and take you with me. *(Lust)*

Helena : Don't say that . Don't you love Hermia? *(Concerned)*

Lysander: Not at all , I love you . You were the one I was meant to find. *(Lust)*

Helena : Is this a new joke? Why would everyone want to make fun of me? I thought you were a nice person to be with, but not anymore. Goodbye,
Lysander.*(storms off)*

Lysander: Wait, my love. Take me with you too.

[Lysander follows Helena and exits through the right of the stage.]

[Enter Bottom with the donkey head through the left of the lower stage]

Bottom: How is it guys?

[Titania wakes up to see him]

Titania : What a beautiful creature you are ? How lovely and wonderful you're made.

Bottom : Who? Me ? I.....

Titania : Sh.....Please make it my honor to have your lovely head have rest on my bed of flowers

[Bottom rushes to the upper stage and sleeps on her lap]

[Enter Oberon and Puck bursting in laughter from the right of the bottom stage]

Oberon: What a beautiful creature ? *(imitates and laughs)*

Puck: Lovely head *(Laughing)* have rest on my bed of flowers

.....

[Oberon stops laughing as Helena enters from the left of the lower stage]

[Helena walks to the center of the lower stage, hurriedly. Lysander rushes behind her.]

Helena : I cannot take this any more, Lysander.

Lysander : But love, I love you.

Helena : You are just making a fool of me.

Lysander: No my star, I love you. *(kneels down on one knee)*

Helena: Stop it, Lysander. I already have enough troubles on my boat. I don't care for more.

[Oberon looks at Puck in anger]

Oberon : To whom did you apply the potion to?

Puck: ah..... I..... didnt get time enough to see the person

Oberon : Look at what you have done?

Puck: Wasn't he the guy ?*(scratching its head)*

[Fed up Oberon applies the potion on to Demetrius's eyes]

[Demetrius wakes up, as Helena crosses him. Demetrius wakes up and looks at Helena.]

Demetrius : Oh! my love you are so beautiful.

Helena: You too, Demetrius

*[Demetrius stand to the left of the lower stage, Helena in the middle and
Lysander to the right of the lower stage.]*

[Hermia wakes up]

Lysander: Why won't you listen to me my love, I love you.

Hermia: What ????????

Demetrius: She has always been my girl

Lysander: I saw her first so , she is my girl

[They stand in anger ready to fight]

Helena: Why is everyone making fun of me ?

Hermia: I close my eyes for sometime and this is what happens.

Titania: Oh my love , I adore you, long ears.

[They all stand still for a few seconds and exit at their respective sides.]

Scene 7

[The stage is empty and slowly the nanny and the children fill the stage with their original position at the beginning of the play.]

Child 1: Oh my God! That must be tough.

Child 2: What did poor Hermia do to deserve something like this ?

Child 3: What happened next ?

Puck: And then.....

Lysander: And then you guys came....

[Children rushing to their parents]

Demetrius : Thanks Puck, for taking care of them

[The children move with their parents to exit, they exit the stage through the audience. Each of the children is holding on to their parents, while exiting narrating the story they just heard.]

[But one of the children, preferably the one who asked for a 'love story', picks up their bag, wears the bag, waves goodbye to Puck, and as they are about to leave, they realise that there is something in the bag. They pause and check their bag to see that it was the love potion.]

[They look at the bottle in amaze, and slowly look at Puck, who is still in their original position, carefully watching every action of the child. Only to wink at the child, hinting to use the potion to create their own love story.]

[The child raises the bottle and looks at the bottle, only to meet their lover's (another child in the day care, preferably the child of the opposite pair) eyes. And shows the bottle to them.]

[The child smirks]

Child 2: True love needs no potion

[The child with the bottle, drops the bottle and runs to embrace Child 2⁷]

Fin.

⁷ Both the children in this scene must be of the same gender.